

Judiciary reform and civic education (civics): The contradictions of democracy, constitution and institutions in Israel

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Abstract

In recent decades, Western countries have witnessed democratic backsliding, often manifested in efforts to restrict the power of the judiciary. Israel, too, has displayed elements of democratic backsliding, peaking in 2023 with an intense public debate over the judiciary's status, driven by the government's reform plan to curtail its power. In this context, the role of civic education, particularly in Israel, where it holds an exceptional place in the national curriculum, becomes critical. Yet, the absence of a shared, consensus-driven understanding of democracy and its institutions, especially the judiciary, among the general population, suggests that civic education has not fulfilled its unifying potential. This article examines key themes, namely, democracy, constitution, and institutions, in the official civics textbooks. The contradictions found between the textbooks regarding the perceptions of these themes reflect the broader divisions within Israeli society regarding the democratic framework and may, in turn, reinforce them. These findings have broader implications for other polarized societies; when fundamental principles are contested, civic education, in its current form, is unlikely to achieve its primary goal of fostering a shared democratic identity. To address this challenge, we argue that elected institutions must first work to establish a minimal consensus on core democratic principles, which can then be reflected and reinforced through civic education.

Keywords

Civic education; civics; judicial reform; democratic backsliding; polarization

Introduction

In recent decades, Western countries have been experiencing democratic backsliding, for various reasons, which is often manifested in limiting the authorities and functions of the judiciary. At the heart of this trend lies a contestation over the separation of powers which is at the core of democracy. Israel, too, has been showing elements of democratic backsliding, for both universal and particular reasons (see, for example, Cohen, 2004; Foa et al., 2020; Kamir, 2020). This trajectory reached a critical point in 2023 with a stormy and polarizing public debate over the judiciary's role, triggered by a proposed governmental reform (framed by its opponents as a "regime overhaul") aiming to narrow its power.

The planned judicial reform focuses on three topics, namely, the composition of the committee for appointing Supreme Court judges, the authority of the Supreme Court to use the "reasonableness standard" to invalidate the decisions of the executive authority, and the Supreme Court's authority to invalidate basic laws. Since all three topics directly pertain to the very definition of democracy, particularly regarding the balance of power between its institutions, both proponents and opponents of the reform framed their positions as defending democracy, while accusing each other of undermining it. This dynamic highlights a profound lack of consensus regarding the meaning of democracy and how it should be protected.

In this context, civic education has gained renewed attention among policymakers, scholars and educators. As a socialization tool, civic education helps students internalize the basic values of society, thereby contributing to the maintenance of the political system (Foster, 1995). Across the Western world, civic education is viewed as a means to foster democratic resilience.

Civic education in Israel, which is mainly taught according to the Ministry of Education *Civics* curriculum, has been assigned an exceptional centrality both in domestic and international terms. While in most OECD countries, it is taught through other subjects and extracurricular activities, with relatively few hours assigned (Bugh, 2015; Thornton, 2005; Tesler, 2005), in Israel it is a mandatory, stand-alone subject in secondary education, included in the matriculation exam (Hoffman and Baron, 2023). Moreover, the number of weekly hours assigned to this subject is relatively high (Ben-Rafael Galanti et al., 2020; Neubauer-Shani, 2022).

The subject's centrality is further reflected in the Israeli context when compared with other mandatory subjects in the humanities (e.g., history, literature, the Bible). While the civics curriculum and its textbooks are common to all state schools in Israel that take the matriculation exam, namely, the state, state-religious, and the Arab school systems¹, such uniformity does not exist for the other subjects.² Given the institutional importance and curricular uniformity of civics in Israel, one might expect it to foster a relatively coherent and shared understanding of democracy, particularly regarding the judiciary's role, thus helping to build a shared civic vocabulary and democratic identity across Israel's diverse populations. Yet, as we have witnessed, this expectation is far from being realized and thus raises a question regarding the educational framework's effectiveness in imparting coherent and comprehensive knowledge regarding basic terms. Against this backdrop, the Israeli case offers a distinct opportunity to examine the potential of civic education to support democratic identity.

¹ The fourth subsystem is the Haredi educational system (Ultra-Orthodox), which has its own curriculum, but its students do not take the matriculation exam.

² https://pop.education.gov.il/tchumey_data/

Based on the assumption that the perspectives conveyed in civics textbooks reflect the prevailing discourse accepted within society, as they are considered reflectors of “legitimate knowledge” endorsed by the state (McCartney et al., 2013), this article aims to answer the question: How are the polarized institutional and public perceptions of democracy, in general, and of the judiciary's role within it, reflected in the civics textbooks in Israel?

Focusing on three core themes—democracy, constitution, and institutions—this study qualitatively examines how these concepts are represented across all three civics textbooks and how they intersect with the political tensions surrounding the 2023 judicial reform.

Findings reveal significant contradictions in the portrayal of key democratic principles. These inconsistencies reflect, and potentially reinforce, the broader divisions within Israeli society regarding the democratic framework. Therefore, in Israel's current climate of institutional and public polarization, civic education may not only fail to mitigate democratic backsliding—it may inadvertently contribute to it, by reflecting societal divisions, especially given its centrality in the Israeli education system.

These findings have broader implications for other polarized societies; when fundamental principles are contested, civic education, in its current framework and format, is unlikely to achieve its primary goal of fostering a shared democratic identity, which is essential for sustaining a democratic system. To move beyond this mutual reflection between public divisions and contradicting civics materials, we propose that policymakers work toward finding common ground on these core principles.

Literature review

Democratic backsliding. According to Freedom House's rankings, since 2005, more democracies have experienced declines in freedom indicators than those that have shown improvement.³ This trend suggests a concerning pattern where young democracies are regressing toward authoritarianism, while older democracies are grappling to conduct themselves (for further reading: Mounk, 2018; Lindberg, 2018; Hennessey and Wittes, 2020; Boyle, 2023), and above all, trust in democracy as the favored system of governance is declining among the public (Blander, 2020).

Regimes vulnerable to regression encompass a broad spectrum of democracies, starting from those that barely meet electoral standards to middle-income countries like Hungary and Poland. Moreover, Western Europe was not immune to these concerns either. The rise of right-wing populist parties across the continent, coupled with the contentious battle over Brexit, sparked apprehensions about the stability and future of democracy in the region (Golder, 2016; Eatwell & Goodwin, 2018).

What was distinctive and concerning about numerous reversals in democratic regimes was the mechanisms through which they unfolded. Instead of abrupt regime changes via classic coups d'état, the regression from democratic rule occurred through a process now termed “backsliding” (Bermeo, 2016; Kaufman & Haggard, 2019; Mechkova et al., 2017; Waldner & Lust, 2018).

This concept denotes the gradual erosion of democratic institutions, regulations, and norms, initiated by legitimately elected governments, often under the influence of an autocratic leader. While backsliding doesn't always lead to full-fledged authoritarianism, in some cases, it has resulted in a complete reversal of democratic progress. (Haggard and Kaufman, 2021).

Two main elements that are associated with democratic backsliding are: the weakening of the judicial checks on the government and affective polarization (e.g., Haggard and Kaufman, 2021; Wagner, 2024; Bermeo, 2016). Kim Lane Scheppelle (2018, 2023) outlines the strategies employed by “autocratic legalists” to undermine liberal constitutions and centralize power. This goal is achieved

³ <https://freedomhouse.org/report/freedom-world/2023/marking-50-years>.

through tyranny under the guise of law, a new type of regime that has flourished in recent years in countries like Poland, Hungary, Russia, Turkey, and Venezuela. Hungary (until the recent 2026 elections) is a good example, as pivotal elections granted full constitutional and executive power to a single party, which started the end of consolidated democracy in East Central Europe, by first attacking the constitutional courts (Kovács and Scheppele, 2018). (For further reading about Hungary, see: Kovács and Scheppele, 2018; Krekó and Enyedi, 2018; Tatham, 2022).

The second element, polarization, is the process whereby the natural diversity of differences within a society is “flattened”, leading to a stark division into two opposing camps. In this process, political identities become intertwined with social identities, minimizing internal variations within each camp (McCoy et al., 2018). While polarization evolves around political or ideological differences, affective polarization involves divisions driven by emotions and identity. In this process, cross-cutting divisions merge with social identities, creating a sharp societal split into two distinct and opposing social camps (Iyengar et al., 2019).

Israel: The debate over the judiciary and democratic backsliding. As previously noted, a key manifestation of democratic backsliding involves the weakening of the judiciary in its relationship with the other two branches of government. In Israel, the role of the judiciary in general, and the Supreme Court (hereinafter: *the Court*) in particular, has been a subject of contention since the 1990s. This dispute has intensified over the years, culminating in the judicial reform, which has been perceived as a threat to the democratic regime.

After the failed attempt to establish a constitution with the declaration of the State, the “Harari Compromise” was accepted (1950), whereby the Knesset enacted basic laws designed to create the infrastructure for the future Israeli constitution (Sapir, 2010). Until the 1990s, basic institutional laws were enacted that defined the system of relations between the governing authorities and their appointment, methods, and powers, and outlined the rules of the game of the Israeli system of government. Attempts to anchor individual rights in the Basic Laws were unsuccessful (Medina, 2016). The prevailing political and legal perception did not see the normative status of the Basic Laws as different from that of ordinary legislation (excluding entrenched ones), and “parliamentary supremacy” was a fundamental principle in the relations of the authorities.

The “constitutional revolution”, which took place during the 1990s, is composed of two pillars: the first, the enactment of two Basic Laws (1992), that for the first time deal with human rights: The Basic Law on Human Dignity and Freedom and the Basic Law on Freedom of Occupation (Navot and Roznai, 2019). These laws provide significant limitations on the Knesset’s legislative power through the limitation clause, which stipulates conditions under which it can violate protected constitutional rights (see: Barak, 1993; Kretzmer, 1992). The second pillar was the precedential ruling in the case of the United Mizrahi Bank (1995), where the Supreme Court ruled that basic laws are superior to regular ones, and thereby, serve as a constitution. Therefore, the Court is authorized to conduct a judicial review and invalidate laws (Jacobsohn, 2000; Sapir, 2009).

Mizrahi’s ruling provoked a serious dispute between judicial activists and *restraintists* in Israel.⁴ The activists claimed that the move strengthens the Court’s role in protecting human rights, which it has been fulfilling since the establishment of the state, and that from now on it would be allowed to invalidate even the laws of the legislative authority in order to protect human rights (Barak, 1999). This is especially important in Israel against the backdrop of the lower level of control over the legislative

⁴ ‘Activists’, are willing to exert their power ‘for their own conception of the social good’, while ‘restraintists’ are focused on ‘expanding the range of allowable judgment for legislatures’ (Schlesinger, 1947: 201).

authority, compared to anywhere else in the world (Cohen, 2018). On the other hand, Friedman (2013) claimed that it was the old, conservative Court that protected human rights more effectively than the new, activist Court, and that the assumption that it protects human rights more than the Knesset is unfounded. In the face of the claim that the protection of rights compromises the sovereignty of the people, Roznai (2022) wrote that the Knesset misuses the authority that was faithfully given to it by the people.

The controversy between restraintists and activists, which had already started before the far-reaching change, was represented and led by two ex-Presidents of the Supreme Court: Moshe Landau (President between 1980-1982) and his opponent, who headed the judicial activism (for further reading on judicial activism see: Schlesinger, 1947; Raymond, 1992; Grimm, 2004), Aharon Barak (President between 1995-2006). They differ in their approaches to three basic themes, namely, democracy, constitution, and institution, as follows: Barak often refers to democracy as a regime characterized and tested in the protection of human rights (*United Mizrahi Bank v. Migdal Cooperative Village*, 1995). Landau argued against him that he was following the path of Plato, who denied democracy (Shavit, 2000). In regard to the constitution, Barak wrote in a ruling in 1990 that laws can be invalidated not only on the basis of the constitution but also if they contradict “fundamental principles of the system” (*Laor Movement v. Speaker of the Knesset*, 1990).

Barak sided with the need for a constitution for Israel, and after the enactment of the Basic Laws in 1992, he claimed that they grant the Court the authority to invalidate laws (*United Mizrahi Bank v. Migdal Cooperative Village*, 1995). Landau argued that the constitution should focus on the institutional arrangement only (Shavit, 2000). Regarding the Basic Laws of 1992, he claimed that the Knesset had no authority to establish a constitution, and in any case, the Basic Laws do not have a superior status (Landau, 5756-1996, 705). As for institutions, Barak (1993) claimed that the Court is the defender of human rights in Israel and a partner in the legislative process, while Landau claimed that the judges have no advantage over parliamentarians in disputes that relate to human rights (Shavit, 2000).

During its first two decades, the proponents of judicial restraint had not led a significant change that would weaken the Court's authority or would change the institutional balances that were created by the constitutional revolution (Mordechay and Roznai, 2017). For different reasons, the Basic Laws of 1992 were not revoked, and the Knesset, in fact, acknowledged itself being constitutionally limited (Roznai, 2017). Even right-wing governments, which, for the most part, identify with a restraintist approach, have been somewhat committed to the activist order of the judicial review and the strong institutions accompanying it (Mordechay and Roznai, 2017).

Nevertheless, a study conducted by Gerber and Givati (2024), based on a unique database about the public's trust in the institutions in Israel, as well as other countries in the years 1991-2018, found that the constitutional revolution in Israel was associated with a dramatic decrease in public trust in the Court. Similarly, Klein (2003) asserted that the constitutional revolution led to demands for the political election of judges as early as the beginning of the century. Thus, the decreasing public's trust in the court system led to a demand for increasing the political component in the judges' appointments (Gerber and Givati, 2024). That is, the wave of opposing the constitutional revolution had started to emerge years before the 2023 storm.

The judiciary's role and status as a bone of contention in Israeli society is also manifested through party platforms (manifestos), which, in democracies, are designed by parties to bridge between citizens' preferences and party policies. While these platforms may not be fully known to voters, they represent the cornerstone of the party's plans and ideas, containing the promises that the

parties commit to uphold thereafter. “Party manifestos matter because they affect the political agenda and steer policy attention towards certain issues” (Walgrave and Nuytemans, 2009:191).

According to public choice theory, bridging between society and politics operates on the assumption that politicians seek to enhance their electoral standing and secure re-election (Downs, 1957). Therefore, when they design party platforms, they tailor the content to align with the sentiments and aspirations of their constituents. Consequently, the collective sum of all party platforms essentially mirrors the prevailing public mood (Pedahzur and Canetti, 2001; Lipshits and Neubauer-Shani, 2019). Over the years, the issue has appeared on the platforms of various parties of both political camps, for example, in the right-wing Ha'ichud Haleumi party's platform (2009), the left-wing Yesh-Atid party's platform (2021), and more prominently, before the elections of 2022, when four parties, representing both political camps, referred in detail to the judiciary's functions and status, giving the issue relatively high priority.⁵

Starting with the 30th government (2003), there have been various suggestions to limit the Court's power of judicial oversight. There are two manifestations of the struggle against judicial activism in Israel: the first, a direct political clash with existing constitutional structures, with the aim of limiting the High Court of Justice's (HCJ) authority of judicial review and invalidating laws, and limiting the *locus standi* to the HCJ. For example, in 2008, there was a change in the method of appointing judges, which, de-facto, gave the coalition representatives and judges the right to veto the appointment of judges. Later, more bills were submitted on this issue. Additionally, politicians have been publicly speaking out against the HCJ (Mordechay and Roznai, 2017). This manifestation peaked with the judicial reform presented by the 37th government (2023), whose three main issues touched upon the relations between the three authorities: the composition of the committee for appointing judges, the authority of the Supreme Court to use the “reasonableness standard” to invalidate the decisions of the executive authority, and the Supreme Court's authority to invalidate basic laws. So far, the limiting of the reasonableness standard had been passed, but was later canceled by the HCJ, due to a wide public protest, while a change in the composition of the committee for appointing Supreme Court judges, had been passed in 2025.

One can find references by the two abovenamed ex-Presidents of the Supreme Court to the three main issues of the suggested reform: first, both presidents opposed the political appointment of judges, albeit Landau warned that Barak's approach would lead to the politicization of the appointment of judges (Landau, 5756-1996). Second, the two disagreed on the use of the reasonableness standard as a tool for judicial review of the executive authority (Dapei Zahav Ltd. v. Israel Broadcasting Authority, Government of Israel, et al. 1980). Third, Barak supported the invalidation of laws while Landau strongly opposed it (Shavit, 2000), as he did on the issue of politicization of judges. Landau warned that the move led by Barak to allow the Court to invalidate Knesset laws would lead to a Knesset override of Court decisions on the legality of legislation in the direction proposed by the present coalition. “A situation of ping pong might be created between the Knesset and the Court, and then, what benefit would we have gained by this law?” (Landau).

The second-order manifestation of the struggle against judicial activism stems from cultural, political, and legal changes that take place in secondary spheres, such as civil society, the media, the educational sphere, and the public sphere, which all contribute to constitutional retrogression.

⁵ It is accepted practice to regard the rank order of sections in the platform as indicating the relative importance the party attributes to the various issues (Lipshits and Neubauer-Shani, 2019). The parties are Hazonut Hadatit, Hamachaneh Hamamlachtit, Ha'avoda, Meretz.

Following the cancellation of the reasonableness standard as part of the judicial reform, several Supreme Court judges have stated in their ruling that Israel is experiencing a democratic backsliding. For example, Judge Yizhak Amit, the new President of the Supreme Court:

“The amendment before us is a single amendment, extracted from the first draft of the proposed Basic Law: The Judiciary. If one examines the amendment to the law against the background of all the proposed amendments, as the Legal Advisor argues, the substantive weight of the amendment and the dangers inherent in it increase manifold. This is because, in such a view, the resulting picture clarifies that this is just one step in a broader legislative framework that profoundly (and perhaps irreversibly) changes the system of checks and balances in our system. According to this approach, the respondents' decision to implement the changes one amendment at a time raises concerns that there is an intention to follow the path of other countries where democracy was weakened and extinguished through a series of processes and changes to governance and democratic norms (for the use of law itself to dismantle democratic governance institutions, see Scheppele, 2023).” (Supreme Court case 5658/23, Movement for Quality Government and others v. The Knesset and others).

Additionally, according to current data, affective polarization has risen by 180 percent since 2009 (Amitai et al., 2025), becoming closely linked to the judicial reform process (Porat, 2023). Consequently, key characteristics of affective polarization (e.g., the merging of political attitudes with social identity, a diminishing capacity for compromise) have become firmly embedded in Israel. Thus, while the judicial reform debate is a significant policy dispute, it has also accelerated affective polarization, amplifying divisions that extend well beyond the reform itself.

Civic and democratic education. One of the key venues in tackling the challenge of democratic backsliding, in general, and the harm to the judiciary's independence, specifically, is civic education, alongside other socialization agents such as media and family (For further reading, see, for example, Janmaat and Hoskins, 2022; Jakubowski, 2021; Muxel, 2022). Civic education constitutes a socialization tool whereby students internalize the customs, skills, perceptions, goals, and values that enable maintaining a given political arrangement (Foster, 1995; see also Bottery, 2000; Finkel, 2002; Milner, 2002).

The long-lasting effects of civic education have been studied by various scholars (see, for example, Torney-Purta, 2004). In this context, Feşnic (2016) analyzed, specifically, the effect of the practices of civic education on the polity level, that is, on democracy. The study compared the teachers' approach towards the importance of civic education and related issues, such as immigration, alongside their teaching practices in Hungary and Poland, two post-communist countries, which were equally ranked in terms of democracy until the mid 2000's. Further, the study empirically examined the voting patterns of the new generations between the years 2001 and 2010 and uncovered notable and enduring cross-generational differences in both countries. In Poland, older generations exhibit stronger authoritarian tendencies. In contrast, in Hungary, younger generations display more authoritarian voting patterns than older ones, a significant explanatory factor for different democratic paths countries take. These results support the argument that civic education plays a crucial role in explaining the divergent democratic trajectories of different countries (Feşnic, 2016).

Against the backdrop of democratic backsliding, the connection between civic education and the stability of democracy finds broad support in Aperia's research (2018), which examined it in 161 countries between the years 1970 and 2013. They also found that civic education serves as a support basis that may strengthen the social foundations of democratic values, through pedagogy that underscores the importance of teaching liberal values.

Studies regarding civic education and education for democracy have been dealing with differing pedagogies and practices of instilling them (Cohen, 2019; Kahne and Westheimer, 2003; Youniss, 2011). Other publications review, analyze, and evaluate policy processes, some of which are comparative (see: Schulz et al., 2008; Torney-Purta et al., 1999).

However, recent years have witnessed a new direction; Gert Biesta (2011) critiques instrumental approaches to civic education that prioritize socialization and measurable outcomes, advocating instead for a democratic pedagogy that fosters subjectification—developing students as autonomous political agents. Building on this, Hedtke (2013) emphasizes the inherently political nature of civic education, warning against its "domestication" into a tool for promoting loyalty to existing structures. Both scholars highlight the importance of embracing political plurality and conflict, offering a critical lens through which to assess civic education's role in divided societies.

In this context, current research studies the increasing gap between the values that underlie programs for civic education or education for democracy, and the political and social culture (Banks, 2017; Fay and Levinson, 2017; Westheimer, 2019), which sometimes undermine contents of education programs (Hoffman, 2020). Furthermore, studies examine questions regarding civic education policy and its implementation. For example, findings show that Hungary combines a declarative commitment to this subject (Kaposi, 2020), alongside implementation that promotes nationalist values at the expense of democratic values (Hoffman and Baron, 2023).

Civics textbooks play a crucial role in instilling in young people the understanding of political institutions and processes within their country, so they can develop critical thinking skills and become active participants in society (Menefee-Libey, 2015). Additionally, by reflecting on the state's past, present, and future aspirations, civics textbooks transmit the state's historical narrative to the next generation. i.e., they serve as a mirror, presenting and reinforcing the basic values and principles that young people will internalize and carry into their futures as citizens of the state.

Moreover, in Israel, the matriculation exams and the marking criteria are based on the textbooks approved by the Ministry. Therefore, even when high school students prepare for their matriculation exams using the Internet, these sources reflect the contents of the textbooks (see, for example, protocols of the civics subject committee 17/9/2015; 2/8/2015).

Following the centrality of civics textbooks, Israeli scholars have investigated the marked changes in the civics curriculum, with a particular focus on textbooks. For instance, Ben-Rafael Galanti and Levkovitz (2014) and Lipshits (2019) conducted analyses comparing civics textbooks, specifically examining the themes of the Jewish state and democracy. Firer (1998), Podeh (2002), and Teff-Seker (2012, 2020) explored the attitude of these textbooks toward Israel's Arab population.

A more recent study by Pinson and Agbaria (2021) sheds light on the changes observed in civics textbooks, in light of the broader social and political controversies within Israeli society. However, no study has explicitly focused on the civics learning materials regarding the subject of the judiciary and its relationship with the legislative and executive authorities.

As we show in this article, and as arguments of the dominant players in the debate demonstrate, the struggle in Israel around the judicial reform is not about the authorities of the Court but rather about the future of democracy. In this dispute, both sides accuse their opponent of destroying Israeli democracy.

In light of the importance civics is given in Israel, coupled with the connection between civic education and the stability of democracy, and against the backdrop of the ongoing public debate regarding the planned judicial reform, rooted in contradicting conceptions of democracy, this study

aims to answer the question: How are the polarized institutional and public perceptions of democracy, in general, and of the judiciary's role within it, reflected in the civics' textbooks in Israel?

Methodology

As discussed earlier, the institutional and public dispute surrounding the judiciary's role had been on the agenda long before the current reform and the public storm it set off. Therefore, the analysis will focus on all the textbooks, which have been serving as the material for the matriculation exam, in order to identify how they address the bones of contention. Therefore, this study employs qualitative analyses of all three textbooks that were approved by the Ministry of Education and that are studied in all public schools: *Government and Politics in Israel: Principles of Citizenship*, by Avraham Diskin, 2011; *Israel: A Jewish and Democratic State*, by David Shahar, 2013; and *To be Citizens in Israel: In a Jewish and Democratic State*, edited by Varda Ashkenazi, 2016.

As previously mentioned, the bones of contention between the two camps touch upon constitutional changes regarding power relations among the three authorities. Therefore, the analysis was conducted on all the parts in the three textbooks that refer to: democracy; constitution and the three authorities. A previous paper examined these bones of contention in the above textbooks, using quantitative analysis (see Lipshits, 2019). The current qualitative complements it, while supporting its findings.

The research utilized thematic analysis to identify and examine key themes that surfaced in the texts. We used a coding procedure that draws upon the theoretical framework regarding democratic backsliding and the debate around judicial activism in Israel (Corbin & Strauss, 1990). It started with open coding, followed by axial coding, in which relationships were developed between the open codes, creating three themes, namely, democracy, constitution, and institutions, alongside the clauses of the proposed reform.

To ensure trustworthiness, each author independently identified themes in the materials. Subsequently, the results were compared, and a consensus was reached to ensure reliability (Rolfe, 2006).

Findings: democracy, constitution, and institutions

Democracy. The democratic regime is one of the three parts of the curriculum (the other two are the Jewish state and the democratic regime in Israel). Below, we will present the focus on learning the topic and defining the concept in the teaching materials. The difference between the textbooks is already evident in the quantitative division of the core chapters in the section on democracy. In Diskin's book, the two main themes are the rule of the people (30.5%) and rights (28.3%). In Shahar's book, the topic of rights is central (40.2%), whereas for Ashkenazi, the two main topics are rights (20.9%) and limiting governmental power.

A perusal of the contents dealing with democracy reveals two completely different orientations toward the term: form of government versus worldview. Diskin's book presents democracy as the far-from-perfect system of government, as he begins and ends his discussion of democracy with Churchill's words: "Democracy is the worst system of government, except for all those other forms that have been tried from time to time" (Diskin, 130,188). The definition that organizes the study of democracy in Diskin's book (131) is taken from Lincoln's Gettysburg Address "government of the people, by the people, for the people". The sovereignty of the people is the only norm that a constitution cannot cancel and remain democratic. Therefore, competitive elections are the necessary condition in all definitions of democracy. The narrow definition of scholars such as Schumpeter (1942)

contents itself with this condition. Lincoln's broad definition adds "for the people", thereby requiring the preservation of the basic rights of the citizens. The duty to preserve equality before the law is emphasized in the broad definition.

At the outset of his discussion of democracy, Shahar follows Lincoln, but at an early stage he moves to defining democracy as a "government of political justice" (Shahar, 159). He and Ashkenazi distinguish between democracy as a form of government and democracy as a humanistic and liberal worldview (Ashkenazi, 123-124). For Shahar (161), democracy as a worldview, "strengthens the chance of achieving the ideal state of true democracy". For Ashkenazi, "the two elements of democracy often clash", but the conclusion is optimistic: "many democracies, including the State of Israel ... constantly work to achieve a fair balance between the two types of values" (124). Thus, both present democracy as an almost perfect system of government.

Constitution. The meaning of democracy is also evident in the books' reference to constitution. In both Shahar and Ashkenazi's books, it appears as part of the chapter on limiting power, and is described as limiting the power of the government. In contrast to them, Diskin (165-166) discusses the constitution within the topic of governmental arrangements, in parallel to a parliamentary or presidential system, a unitary or federal form of government. And so, he writes: "It is worth noting that the vast majority of non-democratic countries in the 20th century had a formal constitution, which ostensibly also respected human rights and the rights of citizens. On the other hand, we come across a few cases of distinctly democratic countries where there is no formal constitution."

Three approaches are presented regarding the relationship between a constitution and democracy: Shahar identifies a constitution with democracy. Diskin shows a lack of correlation between the two and emphasizes that the constitution in a democratic country must not contradict the sovereignty of the people. Ashkenazi displays an ambivalence, though the basic explanation follows Shahar and identifies a constitution with democracy as the equivalent of elections. But she also presents a far-reaching argument against a constitution and presents it as violating the principle of the rule of the people, because it authorizes judges to invalidate laws. The book mentions that there were totalitarian countries that had a constitution.

The discussion about the Court invalidating laws is based on the premise that Israel has a constitution. In describing the Israeli constitution, the three textbooks are similar: There was no (formal) constitution until the "constitutional revolution" in the 1990s, when the Court ruled that all basic laws have the status of a constitution. In all the books, there is a deep disagreement about the "constitutional revolution". However, while Shahar and Ashkenazi bring opinions for and against it, Diskin preceded the discussion on the constitution in Israel with a separate treatment of the concept of the constitution in the discussion on democracy around the world. There, he explained about different forms of a constituent assembly (the founders of the state, a referendum, a special majority, or approval before and after elections.) This is the background to emphasizing the irregularity of accepting a constitution in Israel in a way that is not accepted around the world. Diskin's description is factual, and he does not choose the method of presenting arguments for and against, but rather the description he brings shows more of the problematic nature of the "constitutional revolution".

In the relationship between law and justice, there are differences between the books. For Diskin (181), only a blatant injustice makes the regime undemocratic: "denying the sovereignty of the people, denying the rules of competitive elections, or a 'brutal' violation of civil rights". In contrast, Shahar and Ashkenazi identify in an almost overlapping manner law with justice in democracy. "In the 'substantive rule of law' the content of the laws... complies with the basic principles of justice and morality" (Shahar, 193). Ashkenazi (237), however, brings this position in the name of certain thinkers,

“those who believe that one must ensure that the content of every law is consistent with the liberal idea of human and civil rights”. But she justifies it in the “historical lessons from the Nazi regime in Germany”, so that the teacher and the student identify with it.

In which case are laws not valid? The consensus in all the books is that, according to the pyramid of norms, laws are lower in the hierarchy than a constitution. Therefore, a law that contradicts the constitution is not valid. In Diskin's book, contradiction with the constitution is the only case where a law lacks legal validity. The limitation on the validity of the laws is broader in Shahar (287): “Every law enacted by the legislature must be in accordance with the spirit and content of the constitution”. And the legislature is required to act “within the framework outlined by the constitution, according to its goals and intentions”. Ashkenazi (319) brings a quote from Gavizon, that laws will be repealed “that contradict constitutional values anchored in basic laws”.

Institutions. According to Diskin (169), the purpose of the separation of powers is to limit the power of each of the branches of government. Shahar (280,284) emphasizes the limitation of the power of government, and Ashkenazi (215) emphasizes more strongly the limitation of government when the separation of powers is presented as one of the tools to limit the power of the government, concentrated chiefly in the executive branch.

There are also differences in the explanation of the separation. Diskin (169,252) presents Montesquieu's model and emphasizes the separation between the judiciary and the other two branches. Shahar (419) describes, with reservations, the situation in Israel as “the concept of the separation of authorities as it is expressed in the State of Israel is a flexible concept. Perhaps too flexible... one cannot find in it the application of complete independence in the field of expertise of each authority”. Ashkenazi (217) does not disapprove of “mixing of powers...we find in all three authorities a secondary preoccupation with the powers characteristic of the other authorities. The rule is that each authority has a unique - but not exclusive – authority”.

All of the textbooks see citizens' rights as something required in a democracy in its broad context. Here, we will present the relationship between the governing authorities and the basic democratic requirement of protecting rights.

Diskin devoted an entire chapter in his book to Human Rights in Israel, which states: “When we come to examine the attitude of Israeli democracy to the issue of human rights, we must relate to the state's foundational obligations, to legislation, to the behavior of the authorities, including the executive authority in practice and the rulings of the courts”. The chapter presents the judicial rulings that were landmarks in the first fifty years of the State, alongside laws, basic laws, and institutions established by the Knesset to promote rights. According to Diskin, *all* government authorities work to protect human rights and minority rights.

Conversely, in the other books, mainly the Court is described as protecting the rights of the citizens *from* the executive authority. Among the functions of the Court is “to protect the citizens against arbitrary actions of the executive branch” (Shahar, 404). In addition, in his book (412), there is a sub-section entitled “High Court - defender of the fundamental rights of the individual in Israel”. Ashkenazi (402) enumerates among the Court's functions, protecting both human rights and civil rights, which, in Israel, are protected by the Supreme Court. Although in the basic explanation, both books follow the path that sees the Court as the protector of human and civil rights worldwide, and in Israel in particular, Ashkenazi also has a reservation: “There is no absolute guarantee that the Court... will protect human rights more than the legislator” (Ashkenazi, 316).

The differences between the textbooks are evident in the question of the centrality of legislation in the Knesset's functions and the centrality of the Knesset in legislation, giving rise to the different attitudes towards the court as a reflection of the Knesset laws or a partner in creating them.

The centrality of legislation among the functions of the Knesset. Diskin (231) emphasizes the identification of the legislature and legislation. He defines the functions of the Knesset as legislation and supervision of the executive authority. In contrast, Ashkenazi (349) lists six functions and Shahar (361-362) lists nine, of which only one is legislation.

The centrality of the Knesset in legislation. Following Montesquieu, Diskin (168) wrote that it is the legislative authority that determines "the binding norms on behalf of the state". On the other hand, Shahar (419) wrote: "The Knesset will legislate, but not exclusively". Ashkenazi (218) presents the partnership in legislation between the legislator and the judge who "acts according to the laws established by the legislative authority. At the same time, the courts balance and restrain the parliament".

The Court: reflects the Knesset laws or is a partner in creating them. Diskin (168) described the Court as decision-maker in disputes (civil and criminal) regarding the facts, and it rules according to the binding norms. Shahar (420) asserts that the judiciary "engages in legislation called judicial legislation through the interpretation of Knesset laws". Ashkenazi (216) ranked interpretation as the first function of the judiciary. However, the two latter do not present the Court's activity as consensual. Shahar (401) presents two approaches to the rule of law in the view of the judges: one is formalistic, that is, "judgment that adheres to the language of the law only", and the other is activist, which seeks to interpret the law and give it an expansive meaning "based on the democratic principles and values of society". Ashkenazi (411-412) presents this as a change from the Court as it was until the 1970s, which saw "the legal decision as an objective application of the language of the law", to the activist Court, which "aspires...to be a central and directive factor in society...through broad interpretation."

Judicial activism: the judge as executive and legislator. Diskin's description of judicial activism is rife with between-the-lines criticism. For example, (Diskin, 248): "The Court greatly increased its powers...sometimes based on changes in legislation and much more often, not on such a basis". Or: "In the debates on accepting the law... the possibility was raised to include in it an explicit reference to the right to equality... the Knesset decided not to include the matter of equality in the law. But the court interpreted the right to dignity as a right that also includes aspects of the general right to equality" (Diskin, 220).

Regarding the executive branch, Diskin (251) writes that the revolution is even deeper. In the past, the Court intervened in exceptional cases to protect rights while limiting these cases to the fulfillment of three conditions: "locus standi"; that the issue is "judicable", and by stating that it is not re-examining the authority's decision but its legality. However, "all these restrictions no longer exist".

Shahar (413) describes judicial activism as arising from a crisis in the political system, which obliged the Court to fill the void, as a solution to the main issues of discussion. However, he adds that activism harms the status of the Court, harms legal certainty, and amasses unlimited power in the hands of the judiciary. Ashkenazi (411-412) refers to the aim of judicial activism and expands on the arguments for and against it, the core of which is the question of which authority represents the people: the judiciary or the legislative (413). "The Court expresses the values and will of the people. The decision of the judges is objective and professional – and the elected representatives of the people are less suited to discuss questions of value" (414). On the other hand, "repealing laws harms the principle of the rule of the people - the legislative authority should be the strongest in a democratic country" (Ashkenazi, 414).

In contrast to Ashkenazi and Shahar, who present an ambivalent position to activism, Diskin (253) was unequivocal in his criticism and concluded, regarding the issues that are at the center of the changes initiated by the 37th government: “the judicial authority in Israel enjoys not only extraordinary independence compared to other democratic countries, but also unique power”.

Table 1. Comparison of the three textbooks.

		Diskin	Shahar	Ashkenazi
Definition of democracy	Narrow	Competitive elections	Form of government	
	Wide	Protecting the basic citizens' rights	Liberal-humanistic worldview	
Assessment of democracy		Worst form of government except for all others that have been tried	Government of political justice	A fair balance between the rule of the people and humanism
The laws in democracy		There is no gross violation of civil rights	Moral and just	
Constitution and invalidating laws		Law contradicting the constitution		
			A law should be in accordance with the spirit, goals, and intentions of the constitution	
Separation of powers	Limiting	Each of the authorities	Mainly the executive	
	Legislation	Legislative authority	Legislative authority and the judiciary	
	Judiciary role	To rule according to the parliament's laws		
			To interpret laws. Allowing the values of the judges to be added to the interpretation is disputed	
The branch that protects human rights		All 3 branches	Mainly judiciary, whose functions include protecting citizens' rights from executive authority	

Discussion

While the Court's independence appears as fundamental to democracy in all the textbooks, judicial activism was presented as controversial. This is reflected in addressing the three proposals for changes (reform), namely, the existing constitutional situation and the Court's authority to invalidate laws, its increasing involvement through the criticism of the “reasonableness of decisions”, as well as the composition of the Judicial Selection Committee. At first glance, it seems as if these differences reflect the legitimate public controversy regarding the desired nature of the judicial system in terms of power and autonomy. However, a deeper look reveals that three of the differences concern the rules of the democratic game, that is, the framework of this system.

Eisenstadt (2002) pointed out that a modern democratic country must find a balance between stability and consistency on the one hand, and competition for power among different groups on the other. Therefore, we need to establish rules that balance these factors. In other words, the framework of the democratic system should be consensual and not subject to question, to allow for changes driven by differing worldviews and opinions inside it. In line with this distinction, it is clear that while some topics that appear in the textbooks may be addressed differently, and thus, reflect and maintain

a healthy pluralism, topics that pertain to the framework of democracy should be similar, if not identical, in all of the textbooks, in order to maintain the stability of the democratic framework.

The three topics that touch upon the rules of the democratic game, around which there are fundamental differences, are: What is democracy? Who is the legislative body? Separation of powers, checks and balances: Of whom?

For Diskin, the rule of the people is central to democracy, along with the requirement to maintain basic rights. Indeed, a regime that blatantly violates civil rights is not democratic, but following Churchill, he reiterated that democracy is not perfect. Shahar and Ashkenazi offer a more optimistic picture of democracy, different about its essence. Rights are the heart of democracies, and citizens are guaranteed “political justice, equal and just laws”. Limiting the power of government is more important than the rule of the people because the government tends to infringe upon rights.

A second fundamental topic that stems from the first one deals with the identity of the legislature. The perception one adopts of the essence of democracy affects their perception of who the legislative body is. If the rule of the people is the essence of democracy, then it is crucial that only the public's representatives legislate. However, if rights constitute the essentials of democracy, and the judiciary is the authority protecting them, then it should be part of this process. Diskin holds that it is the legislative authority that determines the binding norms on behalf of the state. By writing this, he sees the Court's fundamental function as the decision-maker in disputes based on these binding norms. As opposed to Diskin, Shahar presents the interpretation of the Court as judicial legislation, and Ashkenazi even speaks of the partnership in legislation between the legislator and the judge, ranking this interpretation as the first function of the judiciary.

The third element of the framework deals with the purpose of the separation of powers. All the textbooks agree that limiting the government is a fundamental principle of democracy, whose absence indicates tyranny, but who is the 'government' that needs to be checked and balanced? According to Shahar and Ashkenazi, the executive branch is the one that requires restraint, because the judiciary is the protector of rights, which are the core of democracy, and therefore, it shouldn't be restrained. In contrast, Diskin presents the need to restrain each of the branches. When one branch of government has no checks over its power, even if it is the judiciary, the regime is prone to the danger of tyranny, as Montesquieu warned.

To grasp the dramatic significance of the dispute, it is crucial to highlight how the two approaches (Diskin versus Shahar and Ashkenazi) expressed in the textbooks view each other. According to Diskin, a regime in which the people's sovereignty is not a fundamental part is not a democracy. Similarly, a situation where the judicial authority is not limited contradicts Montesquieu's principles and the necessary 'checks and balances' that are fundamental to democracy, as well as the expropriation of the fundamental legislative role from the legislative branch. Shahar and Ashkenazi, on the other hand, view the Court as the guardian of rights in Israel, with rights being central to democracy. Limiting its power, particularly by expropriating its authority to legislate, undermines the judiciary's role in protecting rights, which are the core of democracy.

Conclusion

The contradictions found in the learning materials reflect the broader divisions within Israeli society regarding the democratic framework and, in turn, may reinforce these divisions. While civic education is typically viewed as shaping shared civic perceptions among society, this case highlights the reciprocal reflection between society and the subject's content. This dynamic is also reflected in the field of research. As mentioned earlier, most research examines how civic education influences political

perceptions. However, evidence suggests a reverse effect—where political perceptions shape the development of civic education (see: Journell, 2010; McAvoy and Hess, 2013). This reciprocal relationship underscores the intricate dynamics between civic education and the broader political landscape.

At its best, civic education helps socialize societal values and principles. However, when these are in dispute, civic education, *in its current form*, is unlikely to fulfill its primary goal of fostering a shared democratic identity essential for sustaining the democratic system. In other words, under conditions of a polarized society, deeply divided over the rules of the democratic game, particularly regarding the relationship between the elected branches and the judiciary, civic education absorbs and internalizes these disputes and contradicting perceptions, ultimately failing to fulfill its potential in shaping democratic norms. This supports the argument made by Öztürk et al. (2023) that civic education interventions are more effective in fostering positive changes in democratic orientations in less polarized contexts. This situation suggests that institutional and public polarization, an element associated with democratic backsliding, may be driving educational divergence, which, in turn, further intensifies polarization. As a result, there appears to be little prospect of reversing this trend, particularly regarding the threat to the judiciary.

This pattern is now evident in Israel, where the central role of civics in the education system does not shield it from political tensions. Without institutional consensus on basic democratic principles and values, civic education risks becoming another arena of contestation. Therefore, to move beyond this situation, a profound change should be carried out in the political venue.

The elected institutions should strive to reach a consensual perception of their country's fundamental political values. In the Israeli context, for example, there is an urgent need to enact the "Basic Law: The Legislation", which would establish clear criteria for invalidating basic laws. This necessity has been emphasized by Supreme Court justices on both sides when they invalidated the basic law regarding the reasonableness standard, concerning the reasonableness standard, with an 8-7 majority (Supreme Court case 5658/23, Movement for Quality Government and others v. The Knesset and others).

Whilst the democratic system is currently being questioned in many countries, due to populism and illiberal trends, the Israeli lesson should be well taught. These countries should examine the deep understanding of 'democracy' in society, which is reflected in teaching materials of civic education. In the absence of consensus regarding the essence of this regime, and the desired power of each of its authorities, especially the judiciary, the stability of the democratic system's foundations is at risk. Recognizing this situation is a crucial first step toward reversing the trend, to be followed by context-dependent measures implemented by elected institutions, aimed at fostering a shared understanding of the fundamental political values.

References

- Amitai, Yair, Gidron, Noam, and Omer Yair. 2025. "Political polarization in Israel, 1992–2022". In *The Elections in Israel 2022*, edited by Noam Gidron, Gideon Rahat, and Michal Shamir, 21-41. London: Routledge.
- Apergis, Nicholas. 2018. "Education and Democracy: New Evidence from 161 Countries." *Economic Modelling* 71: 59–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2017.12.001>.
- Ashkenazi, Varda, ed. 2016. *Lihyot Ezrahim b'Yisrael: Bamedina Yehudit ve-Demokratit [To Be Citizens in Israel: In a Jewish and Democratic State]*. Jerusalem: Ministry of Education.

- Banks, James A. 2017. *Citizenship Education and Global Migration: Implications for Theory, Research, and Teaching*. Washington, DC: American Educational Research Association.
- Barak, Aharon. 1993. "About Constitutional Thinking." *Hamishpat*, 1(10): 45–58.
- Barak, Aharon. 1999. "Fifty Years of Adjudication in Israel." *Alei Mishpat*, 1(1): 9–17.
- Ben-Rafael Galanti, Sigal, and Alon Levkowitz. 2014. "Textbooks in Teaching Civics: Checks and Balances between 'Jewish State' and 'Democracy.'" In *Gate Keepers of Civics: The Voices of Civics Pedagogues*, edited by Nissan Naveh and Yigal Harel, 11–35. Even Yehuda: Reches.
- Bermeo, Nancy. 2016. "On Democratic Backsliding." *Journal of Democracy*, 27(1): 5–19. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jod.2016.0012>.
- Biesta, Gert. 2011. *Learning Democracy in School and Society: Education, Lifelong Learning, and the Politics of Citizenship*. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers..
- Blander, Dana. 2020. *The Fragility of Liberal Democracy*. Jerusalem: Israel Democracy Institute.
- Bottery, Mike. 2000. "Values Education." In *Teaching Values and Citizenship across the Curriculum: Educating Children for the World*, edited by Richard Bailey, 3–13. London: Kogan Page.
- Boyle, Michael J. 2023. "America and the Illiberal Order after Trump." *Survival*, 62(6): 51-76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00396338.2020.1851085>.
- Bugh, George E. 2015. "Models of Civic Education in America." In *Civic Education in the Twenty-First Century: A Multidimensional Inquiry*, edited by Michael T. Rogers and Donald M. Gooch, 85–110. Lanham, MD: Lexington Books.
- Cohen, Asher. 2004. "Changes in the Orthodox Camp and Their Influence on the Deepening Religious–Secular Schism at the Outset of the Twenty-First Century." In *Critical Issues in Israeli Society*, edited by Alan Dowty, 71–94. Westport, CT: Praeger.
- Cohen, Amichai. 2018. *The Override Clause: Checks and Balances of the Political Institutions and of the Judiciary*. Jerusalem: Israel Democracy Institute.
- Cohen, Aviv. 2019. "Typologies of Citizenship and Civic Education: From Ideal Types to a Reflective Tool." In *The Palgrave Handbook of Citizenship and Education*, edited by Andrew Peterson, Garth Stahl, and Hannah Soong, 1–18. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-67905-1_43-1.
- Corbin, Juliet M., and Anselm Strauss. 1990. "Grounded Theory Research: Procedures, Canons, and Evaluative Criteria." *Qualitative Sociology*, 13(1): 3–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00988593>.
- Diskin, Abraham. 2011. *Mishtar ve-Politika be-Yisrael: Yesodot ha-Ezrahut [Government and Politics in Israel: Principles of Citizenship]*. Jerusalem: Magid Publishers.
- Downs, Anthony. 1957. "An Economic Theory of Political Action in a Democracy." *Journal of Political Economy* 65 (2): 135–150. <https://doi.org/10.1086/257897>.
- Eisenstadt, Shmuel Noah. 2002. *Paradoxes of Democracy: Fragility, Continuity and Change*. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson Center Press; Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Eatwell, Roger, and Matthew Goodwin. 2018. *National Populism: The Revolt against Liberal Democracy*. London: Penguin.
- Fay, Jessica, and Meira Levinson. 2017. "Teaching Democracy in Polarizing Times." *Educational Leadership*, 75(3): 62–67.
- Fesnic, Florin N. 2016. "Can Civic Education Make a Difference for Democracy? Hungary and Poland Compared." *Political Studies* 64 (4): 966–978. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9248.12215>.
- Finkel, Steven E. 2002. "Civic Education and the Mobilization of Political Participation in Developing Democracies." *Journal of Politics* 64 (4): 994–1020. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2508.00160>.

- Firer, Ruth. 1998. "Human Rights in History and Civics Textbooks: The Case of Israel." *Curriculum Inquiry* 28 (2): 195–208.
- Foa, Roberto Stefan, Andrew Klassen, Micheal Slade, Alex Rand, and Rosie Collins. 2020. *The Global Satisfaction with Democracy Report 2020*. Cambridge: Centre for the Future of Democracy. <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.90179>.
- Foster, David. 1995. "Civic Education." In *The Encyclopedia of Democracy*, edited by Seymour Martin Lipset, vol. 4, 156–182. Washington, DC: Congressional Quarterly.
- Gerber, Aharon, and Yehonatan Givati. 2024. "How Did the Constitutional Revolution Influence Trust in the Court?" *Mishpatim*, 53: 277–326.
- Grimm, Dieter. 2004. "Judicial Activism." In *Judges in Contemporary Democracy: An International Conversation*, edited by Robert Badinter and Stephen Breyer. New York: New York University Press.
- Friedmann, Daniel. 2013. *The Purse and the Sword: The Trials of the Israeli Legal Revolution*. Tel Aviv: Miskal–Yedioth Ahronoth Books and Chemed Books.
- Haggard, Stephan, and Robert R. Kaufman. 2021. *Backsliding: Democratic Regress in the Contemporary World*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108957809>.
- Hedtke, Reinhold. 2013. "Who Is Afraid of a Non-Conformist Youth? The Right to Dissent and to Not Participate." In *Education for Civic and Political Participation: A Critical Approach*, edited by Reinhold Hedtke and Tatjana Zimenkova, 54–78. London: Routledge.
- Hennessey, Susan, and Benjamin Wittes. 2020. *Unmaking the Presidency: Donald Trump's War on the World's Most Powerful Office*. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux.
- Hoffman, Tammy. 2020. *Civic Education and Education for Democracy in the Education System: Statement of Principles*. Jerusalem: Israel Democracy Institute.
- Hoffman, Tammy, and Meital Baron. 2023. *Policy Plans for Civic Education and Education for Democracy: A Comparative Study*. Jerusalem: Israel Democracy Institute.
- Iyengar, Shanto, Yphtach Lelkes, Matthew Levendusky, Neil Malhotra, and Sean J. Westwood. 2019. "The Origins and Consequences of Affective Polarization in the United States." *Annual Review of Political Science*, 22: 129–146. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-051117-073034>.
- Jacobsohn, Gary Jeffrey. 2000. "After the Revolution." *Israel Law Review*, 34(2): 139–169. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021223700011936>.
- Janmaat, Jan Germen, and Bryony Hoskins. 2022. "The Changing Impact of Family Background on Political Engagement during Adolescence and Early Adulthood." *Social Forces*, 101(1): 227–251. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sf/soab112>.
- Jakubowski, Jakub. 2021. "Political Socialization in Meme Times: Adolescents and the Sources of Knowledge Concerning Politics." *Review of Education, Pedagogy, and Cultural Studies*, 43(3): 254–274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714413.2021.1872315>.
- Journell, Wayne. 2010. "The Influence of High-Stakes Testing on High School Teachers' Willingness to Incorporate Current Political Events into the Curriculum." *The High School Journal*, 93(3): 111–125. <https://doi.org/10.1353/hsj.0.0048>.
- Kahne, Joseph, and Joel Westheimer. 2003. "Teaching Democracy: What Schools Need to Do." *Phi Delta Kappan*, 85(1): 34–40, 57–66. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003172170308500109>.
- Kamir, Orit. 2020. "Basic Law: Israel as Nation-State—National Honor Defies Human Dignity and Universal Human Rights." *Israel Studies*, 25(3): 213–227. <https://doi.org/10.2979/israelstudies.25.3.18>.

- Kaposi, József. 2020. "Current Issues Concerning Education for Democracy in Hungary." *Hungarian Educational Research Journal*, 10(3): 280–295. <https://doi.org/10.1556/063.2020.00025>.
- Kaufman, Robert R., and Stephan Haggard. 2019. "Democratic Decline in the United States: What Can We Learn from Middle-Income Backsliding?" *Perspectives on Politics*, 17(2): 417–432. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1537592718003377>.
- Klein, Claude. 2003. "A Constitutional Court: Not as Alarmed." *Mechkarei Mishpat*, 19: 497–514.
- Kovács, Kriszta, and Kim Lane Scheppele. 2018. "The Fragility of an Independent Judiciary: Lessons from Hungary and Poland—and the European Union." *Communist and Post-Communist Studies*, 51 (3): 189–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postcomstud.2018.07.005>.
- Krekó, Péter, and Zsolt Enyedi. 2018. "Orbán's Laboratory of Illiberalism." *Journal of Democracy*, 29(3): 39–51. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jod.2018.0043>.
- Kretzmer, David. 1992. "The New Basic Laws on Human Rights: A Mini-Revolution in Israeli Constitutional Law?" *Israel Law Review*, 26(2): 238–246. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2666420>.
- Landau, Moshe. 1996. "Issuing a Constitution to Israel through Court Rulings." *Mishpat u-Mimshal*, 3: 697–712.
- Lindberg, Staffan I. 2018. "The Nature of Democratic Backsliding in Europe." *Carnegie Europe*, July 24. <https://carnegieendowment.org/europe/research/2018/07/the-nature-of-democratic-backsliding-in-europe>.
- Lipshits, Hadar Moshe. 2019. "Realism versus Utopianism in Civics Textbooks." *National Resilience, Politics and Society*, 1(1): 53–80. <https://doi.org/10.26351/NRPS/1/3>.
- Lipshits, Hadar Moshe, and Michal Neubauer-Shani. 2019. "The State–Religion Issue in Israel: Is the Consociational Model Still Alive?" *Israel Affairs*, 25(2): 383–399. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13537121.2019.1577598>.
- McAvoy, Paula, and Diana Hess. 2013. "Classroom Deliberation in an Era of Political Polarization." *Curriculum Inquiry*, 43(1): 14–47. <https://doi.org/10.1111/curi.12000>.
- McCartney, Alison Rios Millett, Elizabeth A. Bennion, and Dick Simpson, eds. 2013. *Teaching Civic Engagement: From Student to Active Citizen*. Washington, DC: American Political Science Association.
- McCoy, Jennifer, Tahmina Rahman, and Murat Somer. 2018. "Polarization and the Global Crisis of Democracy: Common Patterns, Dynamics, and Pernicious Consequences for Democratic Polities." *American Behavioral Scientist*, 62(1): 16–42. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764218759576>.
- Mechkova, Valeriya, Anna Lührmann, and Staffan I. Lindberg. 2017. "How Much Democratic Backsliding?" *Journal of Democracy*, 28(4): 162–169. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jod.2017.0075>.
- Medina, Barak. 2016. *Human Rights Law in Israel*. Jerusalem: Sacher Institute for Legislative Research and Comparative Law and Nevo.
- Menefee-Libey, David. 2015. "High School Civics Textbooks: What We Know versus What We Teach about American Politics and Public Policy." *Journal of Political Science Education*, 11(4): 422–441. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15512169.2015.1072051>.
- Milner, Henry. 2002. *Civic Literacy: How Informed Citizens Make Democracy Work*. Hanover, NH: University Press of New England.
- Mounk, Yascha. 2018. *The People vs. Democracy: Why Our Freedom Is in Danger and How to Save It*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Mordechay, Nadiv, and Yaniv Roznai. 2017. "A Jewish and (Declining) Democratic State? Constitutional Retrogression in Israel." *Maryland Law Review*, 77: 244–291.

- Muxel, Anne. 2022. "Political Socialization and Political Participation." In *The Oxford Handbook of Political Participation*, edited by Marco Giugni and Maria Grasso. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198861126.013.40>.
- Navot, Suzie, and Yaniv Roznai. 2019. "From Supra-Constitutional Principles to the Misuse of Constituent Power in Israel." *European Journal of Law Reform*, 21(3): 403–423. <https://doi.org/10.5553/EJLR/138723702019021003012>.
- Neubauer-Shani, Michal. 2022. "Tackling the Challenge of Liberal Democracy in Israel: The Role of Political Scientists in the Civic Studies Debate." *European Political Science*, 21: 115–131. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41304-021-00336-8>.
- Öztürk, Ahmet, Anja Neundorff, Steven E. Finkel, Elisa Rodríguez Ramírez, and Muhammed H. Eroglu. 2023. "Political Polarization and the Effects of Civic Education." OSF Preprints.
- Pedahzur, Ami, and Daphna Canetti. 2001. "Political Platforms as Exchanges in the Scope of the Functionality of the Israeli Party: Likud and Labor." *Medina ve-Hevra*, 1: 15–31.
- Pinson, Halleli, and Ayman K. Agbaria. 2021. "Ethno-Nationalism in Citizenship Education in Israel: An Analysis of the Official Civics Textbook." *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 42(3): 354–370. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2021.1902277>.
- Podeh, Elie. 2002. *The Arab-Israeli Conflict in Israeli History Textbooks, 1948–2000*. Westport, CT: Bergin & Garvey.
- Porat, Iddo. 2023. "Political Polarisation and the Constitutional Crisis in Israel." *Israel Law Review*, 56(3): 369–84. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021223723000213>.
- Raymond, Walter John. 1992. *Dictionary of Politics: Selected American and Foreign Political and Legal Terms*. Lawrenceville, NJ: Brunswick Publishing.
- Rolfe, Gary. 2006. "Validity, Trustworthiness and Rigour: Quality and the Idea of Qualitative Research." *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 53(3): 304–10. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2006.03727.x>.
- Roznai, Yaniv. 2017. *Unconstitutional Constitutional Amendments: The Limits of Amendment Powers*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Sapir, Gideon. 2009. "Constitutional Revolutions: Israel as a Case-Study." *International Journal of Law in Context*, 5(4): 355–78. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1744552309990218>.
- Sapir, Gideon. 2010. *Constitutional Revolution in Israel: Past, Present and Future*. Tel Aviv: Miskal–Yedioth Ahronoth Books and Chemed Books.
- Scheppele, Kim Lane. 2018. "Autocratic Legalism." *University of Chicago Law Review*, 85(2): 545–584. <https://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/uclrev/vol85/iss2/2>.
- Scheppele, Kim Lane. 2023. "The Life and Death of Constitutions." *Law & Society Review*, 57(4): 423–443. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lasr.12692>.
- Schlesinger, Arthur M., Jr. 1947. *The Supreme Court: 1947*. New York: Time Incorporated.
- Schulz, Wolfram, Julian Fraillon, John Ainley, Bruno Losito, and David Kerr. 2008. *International Civic and Citizenship Education Study: Assessment Framework*. Amsterdam: International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.
- Shahar, Doron. 2010. *Yisrael: Medina Yehudit ve-Demokratit [Israel: A Jewish and Democratic State]*. Or Yehuda: Kinneret.
- Shavit, Ari. 2000. "A Country on the Titanic: An Interview with Moshe Landau." *Haaretz*, October 6.
- Tatham, Allan F. 2022. "The Paradox of Judicial Dialogue with the European Court of Justice in an Illiberal Democracy: The Recent Experience with the Hungarian Constitutional Court." *Revista de Derecho Comunitario Europeo*, 72: 483–517. <https://doi.org/10.18042/cepc/rdce.72.07>.

- Teff-Seker, Yael. 2012. *Peace, Tolerance and the Palestinian "Other" in Israeli Textbooks: IMPACT-SE Update for 2009–2012*. Jerusalem: Institute for Monitoring Peace and Cultural Tolerance in School Education. <https://www.impact-se.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Israel2012.pdf>.
- Teff-Seker, Yael. 2020. "Peace and Conflict in Israeli State-Approved Textbooks: 2000–2018." *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 52(4): 533–550. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2020.1716392>.
- Tesler, Riki. 2005. "Civil Education in a Non-Civil Society: A State Trend, or a Sectoral Game?" *Politika*, 14: 25–49.
- Thornton, Stephen J. 2005. *Teaching Social Studies That Matters: Curriculum for Active Learning*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Torney-Purta, Judith, John Schwille, and Jo-Ann Amadeo, eds. 1999. *Civic Education across Countries: Twenty-Four National Case Studies from the IEA Civic Education Project*. Amsterdam: International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.
- Torney-Purta, Judith. 2004. "Adolescents' Political Socialization in Changing Contexts: An International Study in the Spirit of Nevitt Sanford." *Political Psychology*, 25(3): 465–478. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9221.2004.00380.x>.
- Wagner, Markus. 2024. "Affective Polarization in Europe." *European Political Science Review*, 16(3): 378–392. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1755773923000383>.
- Waldner, David, and Ellen Lust. 2018. "Unwelcome Change: Coming to Terms with Democratic Backsliding." *Annual Review of Political Science*, 21: 93–113. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-050517-114628>.
- Walgrave, Stefaan, and Michiel Nuytemans. 2009. "Friction and Party Manifesto Change in 25 Countries, 1945–98." *American Journal of Political Science*, 53(1): 190–206. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2008.00365.x>.
- Westheimer, Joel. 2019. "Civic Education and the Rise of Populist Nationalism." *Peabody Journal of Education*, 94(1): 4–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0161956X.2019.1553581>.
- Youniss, James. 2011. "Civic Education: What Schools Can Do to Encourage Civic Identity and Action." *Applied Developmental Science*, 15(2): 98–103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2011.560814>.

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